

DEVELOPING STUDENTS MOTIVATION IN EDUCATIONAL AND RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the pedagogical and psychological foundations of the formation and development of student motivation in the process of higher education. Motivation in education is considered one of the main factors determining the student's activity in educational activities, interest in scientific research, independent thinking and creative approach. The study highlights the specific features of internal motives and external motives. Also, the importance of interactive methods, scientific projects, problem-based learning, mentoring systems, innovative technologies and digital educational tools in increasing student motivation in the educational process is scientifically analyzed.*

Keywords: *education, research, educational research, work, motivation, learning process, pedagogical technologies, encouragement, innovative education, paradigm, perspectives, approaches, project method.*

INTRODUCTION. The issue of developing research skills in students in the educational process in higher education occupies a special place in UNESCO's educational programs. At the same time, according to studies conducted by organizations such as the European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA), the European Students' Union (ESU), the European University Association (EUA), and the European Association of Higher Education Institutions (EURASHE), the success of students in developing their research activities depends on choosing the right educational strategy [1,2,3,4,5].

At the center of modern educational paradigms, all attention is focused on the student, and not in vain. Because today's student is tomorrow's society. One of the main goals of education is to develop independent thinking and analytical skills in students. To do this, we need to involve students more in educational research, scientific research and experimental design work. Educational research is a type of independent analytical activity aimed at the systematic study of a current problem, and it is one of the most important elements of pedagogical activity. Research and development - original, specific and planned research conducted with the aim of obtaining new scientific or technical knowledge and ideas.

Experimental and design work - the application of research and development results or other knowledge to plan or design new or significantly improved materials, mechanisms, products, technologies, systems or services before their production or commercial use [6].

Active participation in educational research, scientific research, experimental design work, and project work is one of the conditions for the formation of personal readiness for professional training of students. Therefore, the teacher must ensure that students are interested in research work.

Formation of motivation for educational and research activities in students is one of the central problems of modern education. Its relevance is associated with updating the content of

education, forming methods of independent acquisition of knowledge, developing interests and aspirations in students, combining them through ideological and political, labor and moral education, and forming an active life position. Today, higher education students must have a high level of motivation in educational and research activities, which directs them to self-development and improvement. Motivation in educational and research activities is one of the main elements that leads the student to the goal, contributes to his development and helps him achieve the highest level of development. The formation of motivation in students is a necessary component of the educational process, as a mandatory condition for their implementation of research activities. Psychologists and educators consider research activities in educational institutions as a joint creative activity of the teacher and the student, in which the search for unknown solutions is carried out. In the process of such activities, cultural values are transmitted, the student's worldview is formed, and motivation for general educational activities is developed.

The teacher is the person who organizes the research activities of students and is aimed at forming their internal motivation. This motivation encourages them to consider any problem - scientific or life - from a research perspective. Involving students in research activities teaches them the technology of analyzing situations, helps them choose the most optimal decisions, expands the boundaries of stereotypical thinking, encourages them to see hidden aspects that others do not notice, and forms a creative approach to creating new, non-standard ideas. At the same time, they acquire the skills to act correctly and effectively in complex and unusual situations, that is, the student develops the ability to think innovatively. When involving students in educational and research activities, their abilities and motivation for in-depth study of issues of interest in various fields of science are taken into account. As a result of studying scientific works and articles in the field of directing students to scientific research, it was found that students and masters who want to engage in scientific research in higher education face a number of problems. These problems include the following:

1. Inability to correctly select a topic for scientific research.
2. Inability to define a problem in a scientific research paper and hypotheses to illuminate it.
3. Inability to use scientific research methods and methodologies.
4. Inability to independently prepare a thesis statement for a scientific research paper.
5. Difficulty working with literary and bibliographic sources [7].

Thus, the main goal of research is not to produce a new result or scientific discovery, but to develop the student's personality, to involve him in the world of scientific discoveries. In the process of conducting research work, the scientific supervisor helps students select and formulate a problem, substantiates its relevance and practical significance, and also helps in determining the object, subject, hypothesis and research methods of research. Subsequently, the supervisor provides methodological support for research activities, helps in selecting scientific literature and formalizing the work.

It is important for teachers to arouse students' interest in research, to arm them with the methods of scientific research activity, because in modern conditions, a person is required to independently solve his own problems, find a way out of difficult situations, show initiative and creativity, which serves for successful self-development.

It is now becoming increasingly clear that research and search skills are necessary not only for those whose lives are connected with scientific activity, but for every person. The development of a person's creative potential is possible only if the priorities in education are changed - from studying ready-made knowledge to the activity of students to obtain independent knowledge,

taking into account their abilities and capabilities. One of the main ways to form students' interest in knowledge and independence is the use of methods of educational and research activity in the system of training and additional work.

In our understanding, student research is a form of organizing the educational and educational process, which is associated with solving creative research tasks of students and includes the main stages inherent in scientific research. Research requires the active development of such basic competencies in students as internal research, deep understanding and creative processing of scientific information, working with thought processes, and acting through “trial and error”. The formation of positive motivation for research among higher education students is very important in modern education and the scientific community. This is directly related to a number of factors - the development of science and technology, academic growth and professional prospects, finding solutions to global problems, attracting talented students, and the prestige of education.

Research is a driving force behind progress and innovation in various fields of knowledge. Active participation in research helps develop critical thinking, analytical skills, teamwork, and other important competencies. These skills are invaluable in both academia and industry, and can serve as the foundation for future success in science, education, industry, or government. Supporting research activities by universities and research centers attracts talented and purposeful students. This increases the prestige of the educational institution, contributes to the increase in new funds and resources. Involving students in scientific work increases the prestige of higher education, makes it attractive to the future society. Increasing students' interest and participation in scientific activities helps to develop critical thinking, data analysis, teamwork and other key competencies that will be needed in their future profession. It is important to increase interest in research activities, as well as to form positive motivation. This helps them realize the opportunities for professional growth in the scientific and research field. An increase in the number of students with high interest increases the quality of research projects and work, which results in scientific discoveries and innovations.

METHODOLOGY. This study used observational and quantitative analysis methods. It also used authoritative scientific articles, government reports, and open data from digital platforms to identify the formation of motivations in students in research activities.

RESULTS. Developing positive motivation for research among higher education students is extremely important for the intellectual potential of society and the personal development of future specialists [8]. The main goal of scientific research is to stimulate positive motivation for research among higher education students. This helps to increase their interest, develop their scientific potential, prepare them for professional growth, and improve the quality of their scientific work. The main objectives of the scientific research are to analyze the existing literature and studies on the formation of positive motivation for research activities of higher education students:

1. To consider ways and means of forming positive motivation for higher education students.
2. To determine pedagogical technology for forming positive motivation for research activities in students.
3. To propose methods for assessing the formation of positive motivation for research activities of higher education students.

An ancient Chinese sage says: “Tell me, I forget; show me, I remember; do it myself, I learn.”

According to statistics, how do students retain in memory:

- 20% - what they hear or read;
- 50% - what they observe;
- 90% - what they say, discuss and do in practice.

The implementation of an educational project, as the main object of assessment of results in metascience, is a source of formation and development of motivation for research activities. The project can be carried out individually or in a group, which allows the development of the following skills:

- Social skills: working in a group, cooperating, fulfilling a certain role (being a leader or performer);
- Communication skills: listening, accepting and peacefully defending another point of view;
- Thinking skills: analyzing, generalizing, comparing, classifying, etc.;
- Research skills: conducting research.

The project-based method is used by almost all professors and teachers as a type of teaching technology. "I know why I need everything I learn and where and how I can apply it" - this is the main principle of the modern understanding of the project-based method.

The sequence of work on the project may be as follows:

1. Choosing a topic: the teacher selects and suggests possible topics.
2. Forming creative groups: the teacher unites students who have chosen topics and types of activities, students are grouped according to the topic.
3. Preparing materials for project work: formulating questions, selecting literature.
4. Determining the forms of expressing the results of the project: students discuss the forms of presenting research results in groups: album, almanac, presentation, stand, etc.
5. Working on the project: the teacher advises, coordinates the work, encourages students, students carry out research work.
6. Formalizing the results: students formalize the results in accordance with the accepted rules.
7. Defending the project: the teacher organizes the presentation of students with finished projects and presentations, students present the results of their work.
8. Reflection: the teacher evaluates the activities of students, takes into account their assessments; Each student reflects on the process, taking into account their own and others' assessments.

The best research projects participate in the annual research project competition. The diploma projects are then given the opportunity to participate in competitions and conferences of various levels. This also serves as motivation and increases self-esteem. Research is carried out not only in the areas specified in the curriculum, but also to participate in conferences and competitions of various levels.

CONCLUSION. Studies show that student motivation has a significant impact on the quality of education and the effectiveness of scientific research. The combination of internal and external motivations, the guiding role of the teacher, innovative technologies and interactive methods are the main factors that enhance motivation. Creating a positive psychological environment in educational institutions, taking into account the individual interests of students, and providing them with opportunities for independent research give effective results. The

recommendations presented at the end of the article serve to improve the process of forming and developing motivation, as well as to strengthen students' attitude towards scientific research.

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